

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE

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In reply refer to:
2025-0079689-S7-001

August 20, 2025

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Subject: Formal Consultation for the Eden Landing Ecological Reserve Operations and Maintenance Project (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File No. SPN-2023-00560) Tiering from the South Bay Salt Pond Restoration Project (SBSPRP) Long-term Plan Programmatic Biological Opinion (Service File No. 81420-08-F-0621)

Dear Gregory Brown:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) May 23, 2025, letter requesting formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) to tier the Eden Landing Ecological Reserve (ELER) Operations and Maintenance (O&M) Project (proposed project) in the City of Hayward, Alameda County, California from the South Bay Salt Pond Restoration Project (SBSPRP) Long-term Plan Programmatic Biological Opinion (PBO) (Service File No. 81420-08-F-0621). The Corps determined that the proposed project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris raviventris*) (SMHM), the federally endangered California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) (CRR), the federally endangered California least tern (*Sternula antillarum browni*) (CLT), the federally threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius nivosus nivosus*) (WSP), and the federally endangered San Francisco Bay-Delta distinct population segment (DPS) of the longfin smelt (longfin smelt/longfin smelt DPS; *Spirinchus thaleichthys*). The Corps also determined that the proposed project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the designated critical habitat units for the WSP that is within the proposed project Action Area. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In reviewing this proposed project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps' May 23, 2025, letter requesting reinitiation of consultation; (2) the April 2025, *Eden Landing Ecological Reserve: Operations and Maintenance Biological Assessment* (BA) prepared by the California

Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW); (3) the May 20, 2025, memorandum from Ducks Unlimited (DU) under the subject of *Eden Landing Ecological Reserve Operations and Maintenance*; and (4) other information available to the Service.

The Federal action on which we are consulting is the Corps' reissuance of a five-year Regional General Permit (RGP) to CDFW pursuant to Section 404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 1344 *et seq.*) and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 403 *et seq.*) to conduct ongoing maintenance of salt pond infrastructure at ELER, along the San Francisco Bay Shoreline in Alameda County, California. The previous permit was issued on January 23, 2009, and later extended to February 1, 2024, associated with the 2008 PBO and tiered Phase 1 consultation. An interim permit (Corps File No. SPN-2023-00560) and separate consultation (Service File No. 2022-0003831-S7-001) were issued in the fall of 2024. ELER O&M is described and analyzed programmatically under the 2008 PBO. The intent of this new permit and consultation relative to the PBO is to issue a five-year RGP which would be used to provide annual authorization of proposed maintenance activities. The RGP may be renewed every five years in coordination with the Service and other regulatory agencies, but would not require further section 7 consultation unless the Corps and/or Service determine that reinitiation is warranted. CDFW would continue to submit annual notifications in the spring of each year to allow agency review of all maintenance work proposed for the following 12-month period. The annual work and notification process would be similar to that previously permitted by the Corps in 2009 (Corps File No. SPN-2008-00103) and analyzed by the Service in the PBO. This consultation is intended to tier off of the 2008 PBO and cover these ongoing activities for a minimum of 10 additional years, or longer as determined by Corps and/or Service.

Western Snowy Plover Critical Habitat

Critical habitat for the western snowy plover was designated within the Action Area on July 19, 2012, after the 2008 PBO and Phase 1 consultation were issued. Three critical habitat units occur within the proposed project Action Area. They are designated as subunits CA-13A, CA-13B, and CA-13C. The Service has reviewed the proposed project and its effects to the WSP's designated critical habitat subunits. In designating critical habitat for the WSP, the Service identified the following primary constituent elements (PCEs) essential to the conservation of the species:

PCE #1 is areas that are below heavily vegetated areas or developed areas and above the daily high tides. A component of the proposed project is actively maintaining habitat at elevation levels that support this PCE and benefit the WSP; therefore, reduction in quantity or quality of the PCE is not anticipated to occur.

PCE #2 is shoreline habitat areas for feeding, with no or very sparse vegetation, that are between the annual low tide or low-water flow and annual high tide or high- water flow, subject to inundation but not constantly under water, that support small invertebrates, such as crabs, worms, flies, beetles, spiders, sand hoppers, clams, and ostracods, that are essential food sources. The proposed project is not anticipated to alter or reduce the quantity or quality of the habitats within the subunits.

PCE#3 is surf- or water-deposited organic debris, such as seaweed (including kelp and eelgrass) or driftwood located on open substrates that supports and attracts small invertebrates described in PCE #2 for food, and provides cover or shelter from predators and weather, and assists in

avoidance of detection for nests, chicks, and incubating adults. CDFW actively manages the site to maintain quality habitat for WSP nesting and the rearing of chicks. The proposed project supports this effort and is not anticipated to detrimentally interfere or degrade habitat within the subunits.

PCE #4 is minimal disturbance from the presence of humans, pets, vehicles, or human-attracted predators, which provide relatively undisturbed areas for individual and population growth and for normal behavior. Although the proposed project doesn't minimize disturbance from the presence of humans or vehicles, it does maintain the minimization of disturbance from pets and/or human-attracted predators. The proposed project does not propose to increase human or vehicle disturbance beyond what is already baseline background disturbance levels.

Therefore, based on the above analysis, the Service concurs with the Corps determination that the proposed project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the three designated critical habitat subunits for the WSP. The remainder of this document represents the Service's biological opinion tiering from the PBO on the effects of the proposed project on the SMHM, CRR, CLT, and WSP. The longfin smelt DPS was not proposed or listed at the time the 2008 PBO was issued and the effects of the ELER O&M are addressed below.

CONSULTATION HISTORY

Since SBSPRP implementation and associated multi-agency and partner coordination are ongoing and span over a decade, this section is not all inclusive of meetings or discussions. Those meetings are incorporated by reference and will not be individually identified below. The following section outlines key milestones in the consultation history for the Corps O&M permit for the SBSPRP.

August 12, 2008	The Service issued a (PBO) and tiered consultation (Service File No. 81420-08-F-0621) to the Corps for their permitting actions on the SBSPRP (Corps File Nos. 2007-27703S and 2008-00103S).
January 23, 2009	The Corps issued the SBSPRP O&M Permit No. SPN-2008-00103 to CDFW and the Service's Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge.
February 1, 2019	The Corps issued a 5-year extension on the existing O&M permit (SPN-2008-00103S) associated with the PBO and tiered Phase 1 consultation to February 1, 2024.
January 2024	The Service and Corps discuss O&M permitting and section 7 consultation.
July-November 2024	The Service, Corps, and other agencies and partners discussed O&M and the overall permitting and consultation process and strategy.
August 20, 2024	The Corps requested informal consultation on the interim O&M permit and activities (Corps File No. SPN-2023-00560).

- September 10, 2024 The Service issued an informal consultation concurrence to the Corps on the interim O&M permit and activities (Service File No. 2022-0003831-S7-001 and Corps File No. SPN-2023-00560).
- February-May 2025 The Service, Corps, and other agencies and partners discussed O&M and the overall permitting and consultation process and strategy
- May 23, 2025 The Corps sent the formal consultation request with attachments via email to the Service.
- July-August 2025 The Service, Corps, and partners discussed proposed project details.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

Operations: Managed Ponds

Since 2004, the ponds within the Action Area have been managed by CDFW to provide wildlife habitat while the long-term restoration plan is being implemented. As described in the following sections, most of the pond systems are currently managed to circulate water through existing water control structures, with most intake/outlet structures conveying two-way flows to maintain muted tidal conditions. Other ponds are operated as seasonal ponds which are inundated seasonally with rainfall and flow from adjacent ponds or tidal sloughs and generally also have two-way flow (to maintain desired water levels). Water is released from seasonal ponds as needed. Some ponds in Northern ELER were restored to tidal action as part of Phase 1 project work. Specifically, in 2008 Pond E8A, portions of Pond E8X, and Pond E9 were restored to full tidal action. Ponds E12 and E13 were reconfigured as managed pond systems of varying salinity for shorebird foraging, roosting, and areas for nesting habitat. Ponds E12 and E13 were explicitly set up to test whether some bird species rely on presence of higher salinity ponds in the system. Pond E14 is seasonally managed for western snowy plover.

Maintenance Activities

Various infrastructure and habitat features within ELER require periodic maintenance. Levees need to be maintained for habitat management and protection purposes and for flood risk management, water control structures require maintenance for proper operation, inlet and outlet channels may require dredging on rare occurrences, constructed islands need periodic vegetation control and rebuilding with sediment or habitat enhancement (toppings like oyster shells or gravel), and CDFW needs to be able to respond to emergency situations. Each of these activities require access (by land and/or water) and use of staging and storage areas.

Water-based Equipment Access

Access through the San Francisco Bay (Bay), sloughs, and other channels is required for water-based equipment. This equipment includes boats, floating dredges, and amphibious equipment (e.g., amphibious dredges, amphibious excavators, or vegetation removal equipment). Water-

based equipment access could be required to support access to dredge locks or mobilize dredge equipment to work areas.

Dredge Locks

Dredge locks are small enclosures of open water surrounded by a levee made of dredge spoils, historically used by Cargill Salt and its predecessors. It is not anticipated that these features are used because floating clamshell dredges have not been used by CDFW for routine O&M activities since 2005 and are not expected to be used in the future; however, information on them is provided in the small chance they are utilized. These dredge locks are located adjacent to managed ponds usually within outboard marshes. Dredge locks are used to allow water-based equipment to enter managed ponds for water-based levee maintenance.

To access the dredge locks, a dredge would excavate through the exterior marsh and the levee surrounding the dredge lock. Excavated material would be placed on a berm adjacent to the marsh or mudflat. Once inside the dredge lock, the dredge would close the lock by placing excavated material in the void created upon entering. This would allow the dredge to excavate the exterior levee of a managed pond without breaching it to the Bay or other tidal waters. Once within the contained dredge lock, the exterior pond levee would be excavated to allow the dredge to enter the adjacent managed pond. Earthen levee material stockpiled atop the main levee, from the last time the lock was accessed, would be used to close the dredge lock breach following entry. Upon dredge exit, breaching and closing levees would be completed in reverse order in a similar fashion to that described above.

The salt marsh muds that were excavated and placed at the access cut would be retrieved and placed back into the access cut and channel, closing the lock once the dredge has exited. To gain access to the ponds for maintenance, there may also need to be dredging within shallow sloughs to provide up to four feet of clearance for access. Associated dredge material that cannot be placed on managed pond levees may be used to construct small mounds or islands, within ponds or in the marsh adjacent to the existing slough channel. Any constructed island would be low elevation within shallow slopes, and would be placed along alternating sides of the channel to prevent channel constriction. It is anticipated that mounds or islands would function as high marsh once vegetation is (re)established.

Some slough dredging may also be needed near dredge locks for the purpose of obtaining additional mud to bring the access cut fills to the desired elevation following the dredge access. Advance notification for these unanticipated and very unlikely activities would include the estimated quantity of material to be dredged and placed, and figures indicating where designated areas for stockpiling, placement and borrow material will be located.

Channel Maintenance

Periodic maintenance of inlet and outlet channels that allow water to flow into or out of water control structures could be needed. This would involve dredging any accumulated sediment that is preventing the free flow of water. Accumulated sediment would be placed along levee sides (beaching) or levee tops (topping) as available for maintenance needs within ELER. Specifically, if the excavation site is adjacent to a levee or other upland area, the excavated sediment could potentially be transported for use at another location within ELER. If the excavation site is not

adjacent to a levee or upland areas, the sediment may be used to construct mounds or islands, within marsh or managed ponds, adjacent to the existing channel. Sediment repurposed into an island or mound would be constructed to be as small as possible, low, and gently sloping and would be placed along alternating sides of the excavated channel to prevent channel constriction. It is anticipated that mounds or islands would function as roosting or nesting habitat.

Borrow Ditches

O&M activities in borrow ditches include excavation of accumulated sediment as a source material for levee maintenance, fill to provide access within the ponds, placement of fill to strategically re-direct water to enhance ecological functions, and/or to reduce scour on adjacent levees and avoid needing to do larger repairs in the future. Fill material, placed within borrow ditches, may be sourced onsite (from ponds, ditches) or imported.

Levee Maintenance

Pond levees were not originally constructed to engineered standards, and they require maintenance and recontouring to raise low spots, fill in eroded side slopes, and bring the levee back to a consistent elevation. Levee maintenance would include placement of fill material on levee tops or side slopes in the minimum amount necessary to repair or protect existing levees. Fill material for levee maintenance may be dredged from inside salt ponds (rarely dredged from the outside), the Bay, or slough side of the levee. Fill material may also be imported gravel or imported beneficial reuse material from an offsite source subject to contaminant testing and approval for beneficial reuse in wetlands. Levees may rarely be serviced by a dragline, barge-mounted dredge, an aquatic excavator, or more likely standard land-based construction equipment staged along the levee top. Levee tops could be disked and graded prior to maintenance. Fill (imported or excavated onsite) would be placed in the minimum amount necessary. These actions would explicitly exclude raising levees and flattening side slopes beyond historical norms.

Although most fill is anticipated to be sediments/soils, where necessary, riprap or articulated concrete mat would be placed in the minimum amount necessary to fortify the slopes and prevent erosion of existing levees, particularly in high energy shoreline or slough channel environments. Riprap is typically required on exterior levees exposed to full tidal flows because of continued localized erosion from high wave energy and requires maintenance on a periodic basis. In those locations, new riprap would be comprised of ¼ ton to ½ ton rock installed from the levee toe upwards onto the levee and compacted in place. It is anticipated that riprap would be used to maintain outboard levees of ponds that do not have outboard marsh habitats and that are likely to be restored to tidal circulation in the future, as well as inboard levees if needed. Prior to installation, CDFW would demonstrate that proposed new riprap would be placed below the high tide line and/or high pond level at a slope of about 3:1 where needed, taking care to minimize the number of voids between the rubble that might be utilized by nuisance wildlife species. Riprap placed on areas of non-eroding salt marsh is not proposed.

Water Control Structures

The proposed project may require maintenance, replacement, removal and/or installation of new pipes, culverts, siphons, intake structures, power distribution lines (needed for pumping

facilities), and pumping facilities. Portable pumps, such as diesel-powered pumps, may be used occasionally to support this work, such as supplementing gravity flows through water control structures or dewatering cells or canals to dry out work areas. Dewatering may incorporate the use of cofferdams to isolate the in-water work areas if needed. Placement of riprap would be limited to the minimum amount necessary to protect water control inlets and outlets along the levee system.

Dock and Other Structure Maintenance

Duck hunting blinds, docks, kayak launch, boat launch, viewing platforms and other public access features, power distribution lines, existing marine crossings, existing bridges, bridge foundations and abutments within the network of levees, intake channels, tide gates, ditches, pumps, piers, trestles, walkways, fences, bulkheads, platforms and other facilities would be used, maintained, and replaced in kind on an as needed basis. Structure maintenance would not result in a significant enlargement or increase of square footage over that of the existing dock or other structure. There are a few wooden blinds located in most of the managed ponds in ELER. Blind maintenance would continue to include cleaning out garbage and replacing or repairing boards and support structures using hand tools (hammers and hand-held power tools). Access to the blind(s) would be provided by small boat (or potentially on foot if ponds are dry). Maintenance is infrequent (e.g., once every other year). Maintenance of other existing in-water structures would be limited to a kayak launch (55-foot long x 5 feet wide) and boat dock (82-foot long x 5 feet wide) at Northern ELER; a pedestrian bridge over Mt. Eden Creek in Northern ELER (100-foot long x 10 feet wide); and one mobility impaired accessible hunting blind in Pond E5C in Southern ELER.

Island Maintenance

Constructed islands (i.e., islands created for nesting birds, wind breaks, erosion control) are expected to settle, or erode, over time due to the weak and soft condition of Bay mud and wind wave action. Maintenance is expected to be required periodically to raise the constructed islands if subsidence or erosion is impeding the intended function of the island. Fill material for island maintenance may be dredged from inside managed ponds; imported from an offsite source (subject to sediment testing and approval for beneficial reuse in wetlands); or dredged Bay muds from the exterior, Bay, or slough side of the levee. Islands may be recreated in a different configuration based on data gathered from previous island nesting monitoring within the SBSRP. Habitat substrate, such as coarse sand, oyster shell, gravel, and gypsum fragments, may also be added to islands to improve nesting conditions and control invasive plants. In locations where borrow areas for the constructed islands are near historic channels, the borrow areas would be excavated to connect to these channels. This is expected to facilitate circulation within these borrow areas. In other locations, connections would not be excavated to borrow areas except to facilitate construction access.

Vegetation Management

Non-native plant species occur within the Action Area, some of which have been identified as invasive or potentially invasive. Vegetation management activities would focus on detection and removal of invasive plant species that threaten native habitats and/or alter special-status species or migratory bird habitat. This includes vegetation maintenance on constructed islands (including

native wetland vegetation) or shallow water habitat if it is determined that the vegetation is impeding the intended function of providing nesting and foraging habitat for native waterbirds. Vegetation management may also be required on levees and berms if they become infested with invasive plants. Preferred vegetation management would involve non-mechanized methods of removal including hand-pulling, saline spray, pond flooding (during non-breeding seasons), and substrate-based controls targeting plant growth. Substrate-based controls may include adding layers of coarse sand, oyster shell, gravel, and gypsum fragments on nesting islands. If necessary, managers may use gas- or electric-powered tools such as weed trimmers and mowers or CDFW-approved herbicides. Only Environmental Protection Agency-approved herbicides would be used, and all applications would be by a Qualified Applicator in accordance with the manufacturer's label and CDFW Pesticide Use Recommendations. Herbicide would generally be applied using backpack sprayers or wick applicators, or from spray equipment mounted on a truck or amphibious tracked vehicle (depending on location).

Nuisance Species Management

Predation by a few native and non-native predator species impacts populations of special-status and sensitive species in the South Bay. The level of impact to a species by a particular predator varies by site, depending largely upon the local predator population level, habitat conditions, and surrounding landscape features. Some of the most common predators include: (1) non-native mammals such as red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), Norway rat (*Rattus norvegicus*), roof rat (*Rattus rattus*), and feral cats (*Felis catus*); (2) native mammals such as gray fox (*Urocyon cinereoargenteus*), striped skunk (*Mephitis mephitis*), coyote (*Canis latrans*) and raccoon (*Procyon lotor*); and (3) native birds such as California gull (*Larus californicus*), northern harrier (*Circus hudsonius*), common raven (*Corvus corax*), and American crow (*Corvus brachyrhynchos*). Other less common nuisance species (e.g., Canada geese (*Branta canadensis*)) may have either localized or larger scale impacts to certain special-status or sensitive species. Predator management would occur on an as-needed basis to protect WSP, CLT, CRR, and SMHM colonies. Predator management would also focus on protection of common nesting species to help the SBSRP meet the objective of protection of the breeding birds within the region. Predator management would continue under contract with the U.S. Department of Agriculture, Wildlife Services, which currently includes all species described above, or any newly developed contract.

Routine Inspections

Routine inspections of various infrastructure are required to ensure they are functioning properly, are free of debris or trash obstructions, and are not otherwise damaged or overgrown with undesirable vegetation. Routine inspections are completed by CDFW staff by foot or small vehicle. Infrastructure subject to routine inspections include water control structures, levees and berms, nesting islands, and public amenities (viewing platforms, interpretive signs, trails, gates, and bridges).

Vehicular Access

Most of the potential actions for on-going O&M require the movement of vehicles on graveled and dirt roads within the Action Area, including levee/berm roads. In some cases, heavy equipment such as excavators would be towed on trailers to or walked to work sites. Vehicular

access would be limited to roads above the mean high tide line. Placement of gravel along the levee tops to maintain all-weather vehicular access is required because during the winter months a measurable precipitation can create unsafe conditions or levee damage. Gravel would be placed to the minimum amount necessary, where needed, to maintain safe access along levee top roadways.

Methodologies for Completing Maintenance Activities

Work Area Isolation and Dewatering

Maintenance activities in managed ponds would be isolated from tidal waters by closing intake structures and draining the ponds (to the extent possible) through existing outlet structures (over several tidal cycles) prior to the start of active work. Additional localized dewatering of managed pond work areas, if necessary, would be achieved by: (1) installing earthen or sheet pile cofferdams around the work area; and (2) pumping water from the work area using a portable, generator-powered pump. If used, sheet piles would be preferentially driven in with a vibratory hammer. Water pumped from work areas would either be discharged into other parts of the managed pond (which would remain isolated), or into an adjacent closed pond, where pumped water would be allowed to decant before breaching or connecting to tidal waters. Generally, cofferdams would be approximately 150 linear feet. A similar approach to work area isolation and dewatering to install water control structures in tidal environments would be used, with the additional stipulation that the cofferdam would be closed at low tide to ensure fish are not within the work area.

Excavation

Excavation work to support maintenance activities would be completed through mechanical excavation, hydraulic dredge, or a combination of both. Mechanical excavation would be by excavator or clam-shell dredge, and would be completed after marsh vegetation has been removed from work areas. Mechanical excavation equipment may be staged on the ground mats, or a barge, or may be amphibious. Material excavated by mechanical means would be transported using wheeled or tracked hauling equipment operating on mats. Alternately, a slurry plant located on a barge or scow could be used to mix excavated material with water to allow the resulting slurry to be pumped in a manner similar to hydraulic dredge offloading. All material excavated to support maintenance activities would be repurposed as fill in the Action Area. Hydraulic dredging may be used to maintain intake and outlet channels, both in tidal environments and within managed ponds. Hydraulic dredging would generally be accomplished with a cutterhead dredge, which would consist of a rotating cutting head mounted on the end of an intake pipe.

Prior to beginning hydraulic dredging within tidal water, a dredge would be towed to the site and positioned in the most approximate tidal water body. Once in position, the dredge would be held in place by two to three spuds up to 16 inches in diameter, with anchors (such as standard Danforth anchors) and cables placed off the sides of the dredge to control the pivot motion. Where feasible, the anchors would be placed on upland levees or within the fringe marsh. The dredge is anticipated to have one auxiliary intake that would be screened to prevent entrainment of fish. Fish screens would meet National Marine Fisheries Service's (NMFS) Fish Screen Criteria for Anadromous Salmonids (NMFS 1997). Prior to turning on the hydraulic dredge, the

operator would ensure the dredge heads are as close to the sediment surface as practicable to reduce the entrainment field of the dredge. The discharge pipeline would be connected to the outlet at the back of the dredge. The discharge pipeline is typically fused into 500 to 1,000-foot sections of high-density polyethylene and would be either towed to the site by boat or assembled on the levee top near the work site. Additional sections, if needed, would be attached by bolted watertight flanged connections. The maximum size discharge pipe that anticipated is 18 inches in diameter. The pipeline could float across open water, lay across upland levee, or run along portions of the fringe marsh. If run through a channel, the pipeline would likely lay on the channel bottom during low tide. The pipeline would be allowed to float to facilitate dredge maneuverability but would be held in relative position with standard anchors. As the dredge moves forward along the channel alignments, the pipe would follow the dredge. The discharge end of the pipeline would be pulled forward into the site to adjust the discharge location using a standard excavator or bulldozer on temporary mats, or using an amphibious excavator. It is also anticipated that the discharge pipeline could lay on the channel bottom during low tide.

The slurry generated by the hydraulic dredge could be placed within the managed ponds to create complexity in pond bottom habitat, or incorporated into the existing levees as needed. Slurry material would be allowed to settle on-site; decant water would be allowed to discharge into surface waters once sediment has settled. Once dry, the material may be recontoured by bulldozers or other equipment to achieve desired grade.

Prior to beginning hydraulic dredging within the interior of any managed ponds, water levels would be raised to accommodate a small dredge. The dredge could be hauled into the proposed project area on a flatbed trailer, assembled along the upland levee tops, and placed in the pond by a crane staged on the levee. Alternatively, the dredge could enter through an existing dredge lock. Once in position in the pond, the dredge would be held in place by spuds, anchors, and cables. For dredging activities within the interior of the ponds, anchors would be placed along existing interior upland levees and within the ponds. Slurry generated by dredging would be discharged to another managed pond, allowed to decant, and dry, and recontoured to match pond bottom elevations, as needed.

Pile Driving

Piles could be installed to support maintenance activities. Permanent piles could be installed to repair water control structure walkways or to repair/replace other existing infrastructure. Temporary sheet piles could be placed to dewater tidal work areas required to install/repair/remove water control structures. Piles would be installed using the following methods in order of preference: push into place using the bucket of an excavator, vibratory pile driving, cast-in-place piles, or impact pile driving. Excavator bucket or vibratory hammer installation would be utilized when the piles could be pushed far enough into the ground to be stable. Cast-in-place piles could also be utilized in locations that can easily facilitate the staging of a large drill rig. If cast-in-place piles were installed, a drill rig would be staged within diked marsh habitat on top of wetland mats.

Conservation Measures

CDFW is proposing to implement a number of general conservation measures such as standard Best Management Practices (BMPs), avoidance and minimization of water quality impacts, and

other measures. Please refer to the project BA for these BMPs. The following conservation measures are specific with regard to the SMHM, CRR, CLT, WSP, and longfin smelt DPS:

General Measures:

1. CDFW shall submit to the Service for written approval, the names and resumes of all qualified biologists and biological monitors involved in conducting surveys and/or monitoring work. A qualified biologist is an individual who shall have a minimum of five years of academic training and professional experience in biological sciences and related resource management activities with a minimum of two years conducting surveys for each species that may be present within the proposed project area. A biological monitor is an individual who shall have academic and professional experience in biological sciences and related resource management activities as it pertains to this proposed project, experience with construction-level biological monitoring, be able to recognize species that may be present within the project area and be familiar with the habits and behavior of those species.
2. Supervising construction personnel will participate in a Service-approved worker environmental awareness program. Under this program, construction personnel shall be informed about the presence of special status species and habitats associated with the species and that unlawful take of the animal or destruction of its habitat is a violation of the Federal and State Endangered Species Acts. Prior to construction activities, a qualified biologist approved by the Service shall instruct all construction personnel about: (1) the description and status of the species; (2) the importance of their associated habitats; and (3) a list of measures being taken to reduce impacts to these species during project construction and implementation. The awareness program will apply to construction occurring within or adjacent to tidal marsh or slough habitat and within or adjacent to managed pond habitat. A fact sheet conveying this information shall be prepared for distribution to the construction crew and anyone else who enters the proposed project area. A Service-approved biologist shall be identified as the contact source for any employee or contractor who might encounter a listed species. The biologist shall be identified during the environmental awareness program, and their name and telephone number shall be provided to the Service and CDFW prior to the initiation of any activities.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

1. To minimize effects on SMHM, no ground disturbing work will occur within 50-feet of tidal marsh habitat within two hours before and after extreme high tides (6.5 feet or higher measured at the Golden Gate bridge), when the marsh plain is inundated, to ensure rails and mice have the ability to reach protective cover.
2. To minimize or avoid loss of individual SMHM from any excavation, fill or construction activities in suitable habitat within tidal marsh areas, CDFW will install mouse-proof exclusion fencing or remove marsh vegetation prior to the initiation of work within these areas. Vegetation removal will be limited to the minimum amount necessary to permit the activity to occur. All vegetation within potential habitat for the SMHM within the work area and within a 2-foot buffer around the work area shall be removed either with hand

powered mechanical tools (e.g., weedwhacker) or by excavator. Vegetation shall be removed to bare ground or stubble no higher than 1 inch. A Service-approved biologist will oversee the removal of marsh vegetation to avoid impacts during plant removal. The vegetation removal procedure will be performed as follows: 1) biologists familiar with harvest mice will walk through and inspect vegetation prior to vegetation removal and search for sign of harvest mice or other sensitive wildlife and plants; 2) following inspection, personnel will disturb (e.g., brush) vegetation to force movement of harvest mice into adjacent tidal marsh areas on either side of the construction location. Flushing of vegetation will first occur in the center, then progress toward the two sides of the construction area; 3) personnel will immediately follow vegetation flushing with removal of vegetation using mechanized or non-mechanized hand tools (e.g., weed whacking), which will also be performed beginning in the center and continuing toward the two sides of the work area.

3. An excavator may be used to remove marsh vegetation when vegetation is completely submerged. During these conditions, SMHM are presumed absent from the submerged portion of the marsh. A Service-approved biologist will be present to ensure appropriate water levels have been achieved prior to vegetation removal and are maintained throughout. Access to the submerged tidal marsh with heavy equipment will be limited to areas previously cleared as described in the previous Conservation Measure.
4. Vegetation removed from work areas will be stored in a mouse-proof fenced area, bagged and hauled offsite, or permanently placed in borrow ditches or on the interior slopes of levees. Vegetation placed on the interior slopes of levees will only be placed up to marsh plain elevation (approximately elevation 6.5 feet NAVD88), both to facilitate its utility as a propagule source for restoring tidal marsh and to ensure vegetation is not near the levee top or haul route (top elevation 12-13.5 feet NAVD88). To avoid impacts to mice that may have recolonized the area, placement of cut vegetation on interior levee slopes / borrow ditches will only occur when no additional work in that area is needed.
5. Prior to the initiation of work each day, the Service-approved biologist shall thoroughly inspect the work area and adjacent habitat areas to determine if SMHM are present. Any necessary repairs to the exclusion fencing shall be completed within 24 hours of the initial observance of the damage. Work shall not continue within 300 feet of the damaged exclusion fencing until the fences are repaired and the site is surveyed by a qualified biologist to ensure that SMHM have not entered the work area. In the event SMHM have entered the work area, the Service-approved biologist would contact the CDFW and a Service-approved biologist with an existing valid section 10(a)(1)(A) Recovery Permit for SMHM or CDFW staff would relocate the mice prior to the start of construction in the project area.
6. To the extent practicable, access through pickleweed vegetation will be minimized to avoid the loss of suitable habitat. Anyone accessing SMHM habitat will walk carefully through the marsh avoiding high pickleweed cover and wrack where harvest mice are likely to nest or find cover.
7. Any proposed levee alteration action involves the commitment to maintain intact, to the extent practicable, SMHM corridors (i.e., corridors considered to be connected to larger

areas of SMHM habitat) on at least one side of levees while activities such as levee breaches, levee lowering, or placing dredged material on the levee take place. This would be done to the extent practicable after consultation with the Service and CDFW and identification of suitable corridors.

8. Any large wood, native vegetation, and weed-free topsoil displaced by construction will be stockpiled for use during site restoration. Native vegetation displaced by construction will be stockpiled in areas that cannot be recolonized by SMHM (e.g., behind exclusion fencing, in an offsite storage area, or along interior levee slopes or borrow ditches as a propagule source).

California Ridgway's Rail

1. To minimize or avoid the loss of individual CRR, activities within or adjacent to tidal marsh areas will be avoided during the CRR breeding season from February 1 through August 31 each year unless surveys are conducted to determine CRR locations and CRR territories can be avoided, if the marsh is determined to be unsuitable CRR breeding by a qualified biologist, or if hauling activities (below) are necessary. If breeding CRR are determined to be present, activities will not occur within 700 feet of an identified calling center. If the intervening distance across a major slough channel or across a substantial barrier between the CRR calling center and any activity area is greater than 200 feet, then it may proceed at that location within the breeding season. Exception: Maintenance of novel design features may be performed during the CRR breeding season in areas within or adjacent to CRR breeding habitat with approval of the Service and CDFW under the supervision of a qualified biologist.
2. Hauling activities may occur during the CRR breeding season within the buffer to an identified rail calling center if: (a) there is no other viable haul route available in the Action Area; (b) use of the haul route within the calling center buffer is minimized to the extent possible; (c) hauling along routes within 700 feet of suitable CRR breeding habitat begins prior to the breeding season (February 1), provided safe operating conditions exist; and d) a biological monitor oversees hauling activities, including random inspections, and assures compliance with this measure. A biological monitor may only be used in lieu of buffers to allow for continuous haul truck traffic (i.e., not to serve a discrete/stationary work area within a calling center buffer). Biological monitors on site will be responsible for the following:
 - After February 1 and prior to the completion of protocol level surveys for CRR in a given construction season, a biological monitor will be on site the first week of hauling and at least once a week thereafter, on a random basis, to ensure compliance with this condition. The monitor shall ensure that haul trucks are moving continuously (i.e., that trucks are not stopping on the road, drivers are not leaving their vehicles, and/or workers are not moving around within 700-feet of the marsh), that no other static construction work (i.e., activities other than hauling) is being completed within prescribed buffers, and that vehicle speeds are less than 10 mph.

- After protocol level surveys are complete, a qualified biologist will periodically monitor haul truck traffic that passes within prescribed buffers of any noted calling centers. As above, the focus of the monitoring will be to ensure trucks move continuously and slowly near call centers, and that no static construction work is occurring within the buffers. The biological monitor will be present onsite at least once a week to observe hauling operations and will make monitoring observations from a location that does not unnecessarily stress rails from the monitor's presence.
- The monitor shall verify hauling activities are continuous throughout the breeding season (February 1 to August 31). If hauling activities are delayed for more than 3 days during the breeding season due to site conditions and/or the availability of import material, the monitor will work with CDFW to slowly reinstate truck traffic on haul routes onsite. For example, haul traffic volume may be limited for several days to allow birds to reacclimate to contractor presence.

California Least Tern

1. No activities will be performed within 300 feet of an active CLT nest during the CLT breeding season, April 15 to August 15 (or as determined through surveys). Exception: Maintenance of novel design features may be performed during the CLT breeding season in areas within or adjacent to least tern breeding habitat with approval of the Service and CDFW under the supervision of a qualified biologist.
2. Water-level manipulation (e.g., for management) within ponds known to contain nesting CLT will be monitored closely to ensure that no nests are flooded during the CLT breeding season (April 15 to August 15) unless surveys demonstrate that nesting CLT are absent.

Western Snowy Plover

1. To minimize or avoid the loss of individual WSP, no activities will be performed within at least 600 feet of an active WSP nest during the snowy plover breeding season, March 1 through September 14, but starting earlier or extending later, as determined by surveys. Vehicles driving on levees and pedestrians walking on boardwalks or levees should remain at least 300 feet away from WSP nests and broods. In addition, personnel that must stop at a specific site for brief inspections, maintenance, or monitoring activities should remain 600 feet away from WSP nests and broods. Exception: Maintenance of novel design features may be performed during the snowy plover breeding season in areas within or adjacent to WSP breeding habitat with approval of the Service and CDFW under the supervision of a qualified biologist. If WSP chicks are present and are foraging along any levee that will be accessed by vehicles (e.g., for construction, inspection, or access), vehicle use will be under the supervision of a qualified biologist (to ensure that no chicks are present within the path of the vehicle).
2. Water-level manipulation (e.g., for management) within ponds that contain suitable WSP habitat will not be performed unless surveys are conducted to determine whether they are present during the breeding season (March 1 through September 14). If WSP are present,

any addition of water to the pond will be monitored closely to ensure that no nests are flooded.

Longfin Smelt DPS

1. Work within tidal waters will be restricted to low tide to the extent practicable between May and September, when longfin smelt adults and larval stages are less likely to occur. Exception: (a) the use of an excavator to remove submerged pickleweed (as described above) may occur at higher tides. If this exception is exercised, the bucket would be slowly deployed to allow smelt to leave the work area; or (b) maintenance activities may be completed at low tide when water is not in the work area and fish species are not present.
2. To reduce hydroacoustic effects on native fish, a "soft start" technique will be implemented within tidal waters when using vibratory hammers (e.g., during installation of sheet piles for dewatering activities).
3. If hydraulic dredging is employed within tidal waters, the dredge will have one auxiliary intake that will be screened to prevent entrainment of fish. Fish screens will meet NMFS Fish Screen Criteria for Anadromous Salmonids. Prior to turning on the hydraulic dredge, the operator will ensure the dredge heads are as close to the sediment surface as practicable to reduce the entrainment field of the dredge.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined as "all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action," (50 CFR 402.02). The Action Area encompasses the proposed project footprint as well as surrounding areas potentially affected by the proposed project areas. For the purposes of the effects assessment, the Action Area is located at the ELER, west of the City of Hayward in Alameda County, California, and encompasses approximately 6,034 acres of restored habitats within the ELER (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Project Vicinity ELER Operations and Maintenance

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK for the JEOPARDY DETERMINATION

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a

listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the range wide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current range wide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action but that are not part of the action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3643.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

California Ridgway's Rail

Information about the California Ridgway's rail biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020c). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

California Least Tern

The California least tern is a subspecies of the least tern. The California least tern was federally listed as endangered on October 13, 1970. Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the species is presented in the approved *Revised California Least Tern Recovery Plan* on April 2, 1980 (https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/850927_w%20signature.pdf) (Service 1985). For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the 2020 California least tern 5-year review at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3520.pdf (Service 2020c). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat and degradation being the most significant effect.

Western Snowy Plover

The western snowy plover is a small pale shorebird that nests on beaches and salt pannes in western North America. The Service listed the Pacific Coast population of the snowy plover (i.e., "western snowy plover") as a threatened species in 1993 because of a decline in the breeding population, loss of breeding habitat, and increased depredation by non-native predators. The Service designated critical habitat for the snowy plover in 2005 and revised the critical habitat designation in 2012. Information about the western snowy plover biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for the Pacific Coast Population of the Western Snowy Plover (Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus)*, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/070924_2.pdf (Service 2007). For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the western snowy plover 5-year Review, available at https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/19614.pdf (Service 2024c). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat and degradation being the most significant effect.

The American Ornithological Society maintains the Checklist of North American Birds to standardize nomenclature of bird species, and the Service utilizes this document as our taxonomic authority for North American birds. In July 2024, the American Ornithological Society's North American Classification Committee accepted a proposal to change the genus for western snowy plover due to the paraphyletic nature of the genus *Charadrius* (Chesser *et al.* 2024). The updated scientific name for western snowy plover is *Anarhynchus nivosus nivosus*; however, the Service will continue to use the scientific name *Charadrius nivosus nivosus* for the listed entity until we publish a rule revising the name on the list of endangered and threatened species.

Longfin Smelt DPS

The Service listed the longfin smelt DPS as endangered on July 30, 2024 (Service 2024a). For the comprehensive assessment of the longfin smelt DPS, please refer to the listing rule at <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2024-07-30/pdf/2024-16380.pdf#page=1> and the *Species Status Assessment for the San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of the Longfin Smelt* at <https://ecos.fws.gov/ServCat/DownloadFile/253023> (Service 2024b). The

Service proposed to designate critical habitat for the longfin smelt on January 15, 2025 (Service 2025; <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2025-01-15/pdf/2024-29641.pdf>).

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

South Bay Salt Pond Restoration Project Phase 1 Implementation: All Ponds

Phase 1's restoration actions were completed in December 2010; the last of the public access and recreation features were completed in April 2016. At the end of Phase 1, 1,600 acres of tidal habitats and 1,440 acres of muted tidal habitats were opened to tidal inundation. The tidal areas already show signs of estuarine sedimentation and natural vegetative colonization. These tidal habitats will contribute to the recovery of endangered, threatened, and other special-status species; tidal-marsh-dependent species; and the recovery of South Bay fisheries and water quality. Also, 710 acres of managed ponds were constructed for use by migratory birds at a range of water depths to create a variety of depth, hydrology, and salinity regimes through the use of flow control structures, grading, and other means. In addition, approximately 7 miles of new trail were built, providing new recreational opportunities. Small habitat transition zones were constructed in Eden Landing Pond E14 and vegetated with native upland species. Islands were constructed in Ponds SF2, A16, and E12 and E13.

Eden Landing Ecological Reserve Ponds

The SBSPRP completed restoration of 630 acres of tidal habitat for endangered species (Ponds E8A/E9/E8X) and reconfigured 230 acres of pond habitat for a variety of species including ducks and snowy plovers (Ponds E12/E13). Approximately 3.8 miles of new trail including a seasonal loop trail were built. An interpretive site with raised walkways and viewing platforms overlooking the remnants of the historic salt works was constructed. Finally, a new kayak launch on Mt. Eden Creek was constructed.

Physical Habitats and Biological Conditions

The proposed project occurs throughout the ELER which is made of several types of different habitats. The ELER is directly adjacent to and connected to the open water habitat of the Bay. Naturally occurring narrow stretches of mudflat occur within slough and creek channels and west of the bayfront levee within the Action Area. Covered by shallow water during high tide, these mudflats are exposed during low tide typically supporting 0 to 10 percent cover of cordgrass (*Spartina* sp.) or pickleweed (*Sarcocornia* sp.). The tidal sloughs and channels, including North Creek and Mt. Eden Creek in Northern Eden Landing, which circulate water around the historic

diked baylands and remnant tidal marshes provide important habitat for large numbers of benthic and pelagic invertebrates and fish.

There are areas of mature and newly restored tidal marsh habitat in the Action Area, including areas associated with Old Alameda Creek, Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel, outboard of Ponds E1 and E2, restored Ponds E8A/E9, North Creek Marsh, and Mt. Eden Creek. Diked marsh in the Action Area is a managed system, consisting mostly of the fringe marsh within managed ponds, which is not inundated by the tides. Diked marsh is a mosaic of lower marsh, mid marsh, remnant berms, swales, and pans. The berms are located at a higher elevation than the lower marsh but never transition fully into upland. Low-lying features within the marsh include vegetated swales and non-vegetated pans.

Managed ponds within the Action Area were all former salt-production ponds. Historically, these basins were subject to regular tidal inundation, but following installation of levees and their use as salt ponds, the salinity has increased beyond the tolerance of most halophytic vegetation. Few vascular plant species survive in this environment; those that do include pickleweed, alkali heath, and the non-native small flowered iceplant (*Carpobrotus* spp.), which occur sparsely along the margins of the basins. Because they lack vegetation, managed ponds provide little to no cover for small mammals or reptiles and provide nesting habitat only for species that ground-nest on the levees and the occasional islands that have been created (by deposition of material dredged) within the ponds.

The primary upland habitat in the Action Area is associated with levees. Levees were constructed primarily from native tidal salt marsh soils (silty clay) in the immediate vicinity and may occasionally be reinforced with concrete debris or riprap. Due to the high salinity of these soils and their inherent disturbed nature, many levees feature areas of bare soil or are otherwise populated by non-native halophytic plant species. On levees and portions of levees where freshwater (groundwater or rain) has reduced soil salinity over time, other common ruderal species (non-native species that thrive in areas of disturbance) of forbs and grasses dominate. Native shrubs, such as the coyote bush (*Baccharis pilularis*), may colonize more substantial levees.

As described above, the proposed project is the continuation of O&M activities in the ELER.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

SMHM is likely present, and relatively widespread, in high and middle elevation marsh areas within the Action Area. Trapping surveys in the ELER were conducted in targeted locations over several non-consecutive years from 2012 through 2016. Results of these surveys documented populations of the species in tidal marsh and brackish (diked) marsh in Northern ELER and from west of Pond E1 near Old Alameda Creek within Southern ELER (CDFW 2016). SMHM habitat is present in all tidal marsh and diked marsh throughout the Action Area. The ELER has approximately 790.7 acres of suitable habitat for the SMHM.

California Ridgway's Rail

Occupied breeding habitat for CRR is present in high quality tidal marsh habitat within and adjacent to ELER. More specifically, this species has been documented from the Old Alameda Creek fringe marsh, Whale's Tail North and South, Cargill Marsh, fringe marsh within North Creek, North Creek Marsh, fringe marsh within Mount Eden Creek, Mount Eden Creek Marsh, and Mount Eden Creek Muted Marsh (Olofson Environmental Inc. 2015; McBroom pers. comm. 2021). Current survey results have documented CRR in high densities just downstream of the twenty-tide gates on the wetland island between the two channels that comprise Old Alameda Creek and in lower densities in Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel (Olofson Environmental Inc. 2024). Foraging habitat is present in tidal channels throughout the Action Area. No suitable tidal marsh habitat for CRR currently exists within managed ponds, which lack adequate vegetated cover. The ELER has approximately 1605.7 acres of suitable habitat for the CRR.

California Least Tern

In recent years, a small colony of CLT has established north of ELER, at Hayward Regional Shoreline. Though CLT do not nest in Southern ELER, they do nest in the Northern ELER and consistently forage in the Bay and the deep managed ponds with lower salinity levels and presence of fish. Roosting terns occupy levees of Ponds E1 and E2. These ponds also support foraging habitat for newly fledged terns (San Francisco Bay Bird Observatory (SFBBO) 2019). In 2008-2009, this species attempted to nest in Pond E8A, which is north of Pond E1. This nest was depredated. After Phase 1 enhancement activities were completed in the Northern ELER, CLT have attempted to nest in Pond E14. In 2017, there were 20 to 21 terns that fledged from Pond E14, while in the subsequent two years there were only between one and eight fledged chicks. The 2020 nesting attempt in Pond E14 was unsuccessful in fledging any chicks as most nests were depredated. Similarly, the 2021 nesting season had low nesting success (due to depredation) and only one fledged chick (Ben Pearl pers. comm.). 2023 marked the seventh consecutive year that CLT nested at Pond E14. In 2024, CLT also nested on the levee between Ponds E12 and E13, on a constructed island on Pond E13, and for the first time on pond E6B. The ELER has approximately 700 acres of suitable habitat for the CLT.

Western Snowy Plover

WSP are known to nest within the Action Area and the Northern ELER is where most of the WSP activity occurs. From 2008 to 2014, Phase 1 enhancement activities at Northern ELER included removing potential raptor perches and adding oyster shells to pond bottoms to provide camouflage for nesting plovers and small plover chicks (SFBBO 2009). Oyster shell plots were placed in Ponds E16B, E6B, E6A, and E14 and have successfully increased plover nest abundance and nest success within treatment areas. In 2020, Pond E14 supported 42% of all ELER nests in 2020 (SFBBO 2021). In Southern ELER, the Inland Ponds provide a moderate amount of decent quality breeding habitat for the species, especially Pond E6C. Ponds E6 and E5 are less suitable because they hold water year-round and water control is suboptimal. Water in Pond E6C fully drains/evaporates late in the breeding season, and in 2020 there were nine nests in Pond E6C. Unfortunately, six of those nests were flooded during one event (SFBBO 2021). The ELER has approximately 1908.3 acres of suitable habitat for the WSP.

Longfin Smelt DPS

Longfin smelt have been caught in Coyote Creek and Alviso Slough and could possibly be present in ELER (Hobbs 2012). Suitable habitat for longfin smelt DPS is located in the Bay, Mt. Eden Creek, Mt. Eden Creek Marsh, Mt. Eden Creek Muted Marsh, North Creek, North Creek Marsh, and Old Alameda Creek. The ELER has approximately 259 acres of suitable open water aquatic habitat for the longfin smelt DPS.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. *Effects of the Action* may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

SMHM have the potential to be within the immediate footprint of the various O&M activities of the proposed project and within the considerably large expanse of high quality habitat that occurs on the ELER. The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance from personnel and construction equipment. Equipment noise, vibration, and visual disturbance may interfere with the normal behaviors of SMHM if present in the project area or immediately nearby. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, reproducing, rearing, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Affected SMHM may suffer from increased predation, competition, and reduced reproductive success. Proposed project activities may cause actively nursing mice nearby to abandon their nests leading to mortality of their pups from starvation or predation.

Intolerable levels of disturbance may force individual SMHM to flush from cover and expose themselves to contact with construction personnel and equipment. SMHM that come into contact with construction personnel or equipment are at risk of being trampled or crushed which could result in injury or mortality. SMHM could also get injured or killed if they were to come in contact with vegetation clearing equipment.

CDFW proposes to employ the flushing or hazing of mice to compel them to leave the proposed project area before and during vegetation removal. The act of “flushing” mice could result in injury, mortality, or stressors to individual SMHM that could interfere with normal behaviors. The likelihood of injury or mortality would depend on several factors such as the experience of the biologist or crew member conducting the activity, the methods, and resiliency of the individual SMHM. Even if no injury occurred, active hazing may cause immediate or latent stressors that could result in future harm and reduced survivability to the individual SMHM. This may manifest in adverse behaviors such as not being able to find or seek adequate shelter which could expose them to predation or adversely affecting foraging, feeding or reproductive behaviors.

The proposed project will result in various temporary impacts to suitable habitats within the ELER over the life of the permit depending on the O&M activity and need for ground

disturbance, vegetation clearing, or habitat management. These temporary effects are not expected to have long-term effects and some habitat management activities are anticipated to have beneficial effects for SMHM as CDFW manages the ELER for benefits to the species. Some habitats that have expanded or have temporarily established in a given area and may be suitable for SMHM may need to be altered or modified to benefit another listed species such as CLT or WSP. As such, that habitat may no longer be suitable for the SMHM to utilize if altered or modified for a different species use.

CDFW proposes to implement several *Conservation Measures* for the SMHM which include preconstruction surveys, a Service-approved biologist on site during activities such as vegetation removal, and worker awareness training. These measures reduce, but do not eliminate the potential for adverse effects to the SMHM and may not be sufficient to reduce construction noise, visual disturbance, or physical impacts in areas where SMHM are present.

California Ridgway's Rail

CRR have the potential to be within the immediate footprint of the various O&M activities of the proposed project and within the considerably large expanse of high quality habitat that occurs on the ELER. The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance from personnel and construction equipment. Equipment noise, vibration, and visual disturbance may interfere with the normal behaviors of CRR if present in the project area or immediately nearby. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, courtship, breeding, rearing, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Affected CRR may suffer from increased predation, competition, and reduced reproductive success. O&M activities may temporarily disrupt normal behavior patterns of this species, especially during the breeding season. As breeding is an essential behavior, the Service anticipates that the proposed project activities may cause actively nesting CRR nearby to abandon their nests leading to the loss of viable eggs or mortality of their chicks from starvation or predation. Eggs or chicks lost to nest failure for the CRR may occur due to the nature of the project and that CDFW proposes to conduct some O&M activities within the breeding season if the activity is deemed to be mission critical and necessary. CDFW proposes to conduct CRR nesting surveys during the CRR breeding season and implement disturbance buffers where appropriate. This measure will reduce, but not eliminate the potential for CRR to abandon or expose their nests to predation if they attempt to evade an intolerable disturbance.

Intolerable levels of disturbance may force individual CRR to flush from cover and expose themselves to contact with construction personnel and equipment. CRR that come into contact with construction personnel or equipment are at risk of physical trauma that could result in physical injury and/or mortality.

The proposed project will result in various temporary impacts to suitable habitats within the ELER over the life of the permit depending on the O&M activity and need for ground disturbance, vegetation clearing, or habitat management. These temporary effects are not expected to have long-term effects and some habitat management activities are anticipated to have beneficial effects for CRR as CDFW manages the ELER for benefits to the species. Some habitats that have expanded or have temporarily established in a given area and may be suitable for CRR may need to be altered or modified to benefit another listed species such as CLT or

WSP. As such, that habitat may no longer be suitable for the CRR to utilize if altered or modified for a different species use.

These adverse effects will be partially minimized by the utilization of a Service-approved biological monitor and by educating personnel about the presence of CRR, its preferred habitat, species identification, regulatory laws, and the other proposed *Conservation Measures*. Adverse effects will also be partially minimized by observation of the Service's recommended work window that avoids the breeding season for the CRR and maintaining disturbance buffers when work windows are not feasible.

California Least Tern & Western Snowy Plover

CLT and WSP have the potential to be within the immediate footprint of the various O&M activities of the proposed project and within suitable nesting habitat that occurs on the ELER. The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance from personnel and construction equipment. Equipment noise, vibration, and visual disturbance may interfere with the normal behaviors of CLT and WSP if present in the project area or immediately nearby. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, courtship, breeding, rearing, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Affected CLT and WSP may suffer from increased predation, competition, and reduced reproductive success. O&M activities may temporarily disrupt normal behavior patterns of this species, especially during the breeding season. As breeding is an essential behavior, the Service anticipates that the proposed project activities may cause actively nesting CLT or WSP nearby to abandon their nests leading to the loss of viable eggs or mortality of their chicks from starvation or predation. Eggs or chicks lost to nest failure for the CLT or WSP may occur due to the nature of the project and that CDFW proposes to conduct some O&M activities within the breeding season if the activity is deemed to be mission critical and necessary. CDFW proposes to conduct CLT and WSP nesting surveys during their respective breeding seasons and implement disturbance buffers where appropriate. This measure will reduce, but not eliminate the potential for CLT or WSP to abandon or expose their nests to predation if they attempt to evade an intolerable disturbance.

The proposed project will result in various temporary impacts to suitable habitats within the ELER over the life of the permit depending on the O&M activity and need for ground disturbance, vegetation clearing, or habitat management. These temporary effects are not expected to have long-term effects and some habitat management activities are anticipated to have beneficial effects for CLT and WSP as CDFW manages the ELER for benefits to the species. Some habitats that have expanded or have temporarily established in a given area and may be suitable for CLT and WSP may need to be altered or modified to benefit another listed species such as SMHM or CRR. As such, that habitat may no longer be suitable for the CLT or WSP to utilize if altered or modified for a different species use.

These adverse effects will be partially minimized by the utilization of a Service-approved biological monitor and by educating personnel about the presence of CLT and WSP, their preferred habitats, species identification, regulatory laws, and the other proposed *Conservation Measures*. Adverse effects will also be partially minimized by observation of the Service's recommended work window that avoids the breeding season for the CLT and WSP and maintaining disturbance buffers when work windows are not feasible. Management of water

levels in ponds utilized as nesting habitat for CLT and WSP would be tailored to avoid flooding CLT and/or WSP nests before chicks fledge for the season.

Longfin Smelt DPS

Vibratory noise, sediment plumes and disturbance from operation of the dredger, pumping systems, and pile driving could harm nearby longfin smelt through the interference of essential normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, breeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance may force individual longfin smelt to evade and flush from their position in the aquatic environment or potentially expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. Entrainment of adults, juveniles, larvae and eggs into the dredger suction could result in injury, and/or mortality of longfin smelt.

Vibratory Noise and Sediment Overflow Plume

Vibratory noise caused by mechanical equipment such as dredger head, pumping systems, and pile driving that raise noise levels above ambient levels would likely harm adult and juvenile longfin smelt. Longfin smelt would likely be stressed and resort to evasive behaviors which would interfere with normal sheltering and foraging behaviors. Repeated frequency of dredging events would also increase the frequency of harm and could result in modification of longfin smelt behavior and increase the severity of sublethal effects from stress over time. These sublethal effects can cause a decline in fitness that may make the animal more susceptible to disease and predation. The dredger occupies a very small footprint on the water surface in comparison to the large open water expanse of the Bay. This would allow longfin smelt sufficient space to evade dredging or pile driving operations. CDFW proposes to have their contractors use vibratory pile driving and “push” techniques to the fullest extent possible and would use a “soft start” technique when using vibratory hammers to install sheet piles to minimize effects associated with underwater noise disturbance.

A sediment plume results from excess sediment and other material entrained (e.g. air bubbles) being disturbed in the water during operations. Sediment plumes typically have an increased suspended sediment concentration and elevated turbidity. The degree of sediment resuspension depends on the material, size and composition of the sediment being resuspended. Plume size, concentration, and duration of the plume depend on environmental and operational specific factors. Exposure to excessive suspended sediment concentrations could lead to physiological stresses such as clogged gills, eroded gill and epithelial tissues, impaired foraging activity and feeding success, and altered movement and migration patterns of juvenile and adult fish (Wilber and Clarke 2001; Minello *et al.* 1987; Newcombe and Jensen 1996; Newcombe and MacDonald 1991). Exposure of fish to elevated suspended sediment concentrations could result in behavioral avoidance and exclusion from otherwise suitable habitat, disrupt movement and migration patterns, reduce feeding rates and growth, result in sublethal and lethal physiological stress, habitat degradation, or delayed hatching, and, under severe circumstances, could result in mortality (Newcombe and Jensen 1996; Wilber and Clarke 2001). The response of fish to suspended sediments varies among species and lifestages as a function of suspended particle size, particle shape, water velocities, suspended sediment concentrations, water temperature, depressed dissolved oxygen concentrations, contaminants, and exposure duration (O'Connor 1991; Sherk 1971; Newcombe and Jensen 1996). Short-duration exposure to elevated suspended

sediment concentration associated with sediment plumes could result in sublethal effects; however, potential exposure and dosage of suspended sediment concentrations drops exponentially from the source of the plume. If longfin smelt were present within the sediment plume, the behavioral avoidance response of longfin smelt is expected to substantially reduce or eliminate the risk of lethal or sublethal exposure the farther they are from the plume source.

Entrainment

CDFW proposes to use suction dredging equipment that entrains water and potentially fish to facilitate the creation of the sand-water slurry. The applicants have installed fish screens in compliance with NMFS criteria on the equipment; however, these are criteria for salmonids and may not entirely exclude juvenile and adult longfin smelt from entrainment during dredging events. The suction dredger still has the potential to entrain longfin smelt larvae and eggs into the equipment. Direct effects of entrainment occur only to fishes that are small enough to pass through the intake screen mesh and cannot overcome the intake velocity. Larval longfin smelt and eggs are not expected to be able to overcome the intake velocity if they were within the vortex of the suction. The direct effect of entrainment is mortality of longfin smelt larvae and eggs from passage through the water intake systems. As entrained longfin smelt pass through the water intake system, they can be exposed to several types of stresses that would result in mortality. These include mechanical stress from contact with the internal surfaces of pumps and pipes, pressure stress from exposure to relatively rapid pressure changes, shear stress from exposure to complex water flows, and exposure to the sand and materials being pulled through the pipe.

Dredging harvests spawning substrate where eggs and larvae for longfin smelt could be entrained during a dredging event. It is unknown at what water depths longfin smelt prefer to spawn, but they are known to spawn in the various tidal channels and marshes of the Bay.

There is currently insufficient information with regard to effects to population densities of prey or food web dynamics but the Service assumes some food web loss from entrainment.

Impingement

Impingement can result in mortality of longfin smelt from contact with the intake screens. Impingement occurs when longfin smelt cannot swim away from the intake screens because the intake velocity overcomes their ability to swim away, but the longfin smelt is too large to be entrained. Impingement only occurs to longfin smelt that are large enough that they cannot pass through the intake screen mesh and cannot overcome the intake velocity. Impingement may cause injury, death, or stress on longfin smelt.

The level of entrainment or impingement of adult or juvenile longfin smelt is expected to be very low as they are not expected to be near the substrate bottom where the suction head is proposed to be placed. Entrainment is also expected to be minimized further as CDFW propose to insert the dredger suction head into the substrate or just above the substrate before pumping, reducing the likelihood of adult fish being sucked into the dredger head.

Stranding or Impoundment

If longfin smelt are present in open water habitat within the Action Area during certain work activities (e.g., levee repairs) they may be adversely affected. The proposed project could result in stranding or impoundment during site isolation work and dewatering. Longfin smelt that enter managed ponds may occur under the proposed project. Potential lethal and sublethal effects to these fish include exposure to poor water quality (temperature, salinity, turbidity), increased predation, entrainment and inability to egress. To significantly reduce the potential for longfin smelt to enter the managed ponds, Water control structures will be operated in a two-way fashion to allow fish to exit ponds. CDFW could also modify its current operational practice and close the water control connection between the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel and Pond E2C between December 1 and May 31 to reduce the potential for longfin smelt and other fish to enter these ponds during key migration periods. During this time frame, the Southern Ponds would shift to being managed as seasonal ponds rather than as muted tidal ponds. While these operational measures would significantly reduce potential indirect effects on longfin smelt that may enter managed ponds, this action could affect other species habitat suitability for overwintering waterfowl and migratory shorebirds such as CLT and WSP.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section; they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species*, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Eden Landing Ecological Reserve Operations and Maintenance Project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the SMHM, CRR, CLT, WSP, and longfin smelt. This is based on the baseline condition that O&M activities at the ELER have been on-going activities, the ELER is managed for resident and migratory waterbirds and tidal marsh habitats and species, and implementation of the *Conservation Measures* to minimize the adverse effects on individual SMHM, CRR, CLT, WSP, and the longfin smelt DPS.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of "take" in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3) Under the terms of

section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant (CDFW), as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require CDFW or their contractors to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps and CDFW must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(4)].

Amount or Extent of Take

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The Service anticipates incidental take of SMHM will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, small size, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. In accordance with 50 CFR 402.14(i)(1)(i), a surrogate for individual animals may be used to express the amount or extent of anticipated incidental take in the Incidental Take Statement (ITS). Surrogates are used for this ITS because it is difficult to accurately quantify and monitor the amount or number of individuals that are expected to be incidentally taken as a result of the proposed action. Therefore, the Service is using habitat affected as a surrogate for individual SMHM. The Service anticipates incidental take of all SMHM within the 790.7 acres suitable tidal marsh habitat in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors through the various noise and visual effects of O&M activities which include potential pile driving will occur. The Service anticipates that the number of SMHM adversely affected will be low or minimal, but not completely reduced, based on the conditions of the project and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors within the 790.7 acres of suitable habitat within the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

The Service anticipates that take in the form of wounding or killing of SMHM during O&M activities will occur due to the nature of the project, conducting activities within occupied habitats, and the increased probability of coming in physical contact with a SMHM during O&M activities. Therefore, the Service anticipates that no more than ten (10) SMHM per year will be subject to incidental take in the form of injury and mortality within the Action Area subject to flushing, physical disturbance, and human activity. This number is anticipated to constitute a fractional percentage of the total population of SMHM in the Action Area. *Conservation Measures* proposed by the applicant and described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* will reduce, but not eliminate, the potential for incidental taking of SMHM. Upon implementation of the following *Reasonable and Prudent Measure*, take in the form of injury and mortality of

SMHM within all suitable habitat within the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

California Ridgway's Rail

The Service anticipates incidental take of CRR will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. In accordance with 50 CFR 402.14(i)(1)(i), the Service is using habitat affected as a surrogate for individual CRR. The Service anticipates incidental take of all CRR within the 1605.7 acres of suitable tidal marsh habitat in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors (which includes breeding) through the various noise and visual effects of O&M activities which include potential pile driving will occur. It would also be difficult to quantify the number of anticipated nest failures as O&M activities conducted during the CRR breeding season would be rare and detecting a nest failure would be difficult as CRR nests are not always easy to locate or identify. It could also be difficult to determine whether a failed nest was attributable to O&M activities or some other attributable factor, natural (e.g. predation) or otherwise. The Service anticipates that the number of individual CRR adversely affected from the interference of essential behaviors (to include loss of eggs or chicks through nest failures) will be low or minimal, but not completely reduced, based on the conditions of the project and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors (to include nest failures) within the 1605.7 acres of suitable habitat within the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

The Service does not anticipate that take in the form of wounding or killing of CRR (this does not include loss of eggs or chicks due to nest failure) during O&M activities will occur due to the nature of the project, conducting activities within occupied habitats will be minimal, the low probability of coming in physical contact with a CRR during O&M activities, and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service is not exempting take in the form of wound or kill for any CRR during construction activities from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

California Least Tern and Western Snowy Plover

The Service anticipates incidental take of CLT and WSP will be difficult to quantify because the number of birds detected through surveys can change significantly year over year. In accordance with 50 CFR 402.14(i)(1)(i), the Service is using habitat affected as a surrogate for individual CLT and WSP. The Service anticipates incidental take of all CLT and WSP within the 700 acres of suitable habitat for the CLT and 1908.3 acres of suitable tidal marsh habitats in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors (which includes breeding) through the various noise and visual effects of O&M activities which include potential pile driving will occur. It could also be difficult to determine whether a failed nest was attributable to O&M activities or some other attributable factor, natural (e.g. predation) or otherwise. The Service anticipates that the number of CLT or WSP adversely affected from the interference of essential behaviors (to include loss of eggs or chicks through nest failures) will be low or minimal, but not completely reduced, based on the conditions of the project and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure, take in the

form of harm from impairing essential behaviors (to include nest failures) within the 700 acres of suitable habitat for the CLT and 1908.3 acres of suitable habitat for the WSP within the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

The Service does not anticipate that take in the form of wounding or killing of CLT or WSP (this does not include loss of eggs or chicks due to nest failure) during O&M activities will occur due to the nature of the project, conducting activities within occupied habitats will be minimal, the low probability of coming in physical contact with a CLT and/or WSP during O&M activities, and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service is not exempting take in the form of wound or kill for any CLT or WSP during construction activities from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Longfin Smelt DPS

The Service anticipates incidental take of longfin smelt will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, small size, and their propensity to move rapidly through the open water resulting in low detectability. In accordance with 50 CFR 402.14(i)(1)(i), the Service is using habitat affected as a surrogate for individual longfin smelt. The Service anticipates incidental take of all longfin smelt within the 259 acres of suitable open water aquatic habitat within the Action Area in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors through the various noise and visual effects of O&M activities which include potential pile driving. The Service anticipates that the number of longfin smelt adversely affected will be low or minimal, but not completely reduced, based on the conditions of the project and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors within the 259 acres of suitable open water aquatic habitat within the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

The Service anticipates that take in the form of wounding or killing of longfin smelt during O&M activities will occur due to the nature of the project, conducting activities within occupied habitats, and the increased probability of coming in physical contact with a longfin smelt during O&M activities (e.g. suction dredging). Therefore, the Service anticipates that all life stages of the longfin smelt including eggs will be subject to incidental take in the form of injury and mortality within the 259 acres of suitable open water aquatic habitat within the Action Area subject to physical disturbance and human activity. *Conservation Measures* proposed by the applicant and described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* will reduce, but not eliminate, the potential for incidental taking of longfin smelt. Upon implementation of the following *Reasonable and Prudent Measure*, take in the form of injury and mortality of longfin smelt within the 259 acres of suitable open water aquatic habitat within the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

The Service determines that the level of take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the SMHM, CRR, CLT, WSP, or the longfin smelt DPS.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

The following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project to the salt marsh harvest mouse, California Ridgway's rail, California least tern, western snowy plover, and longfin smelt:

1. The Corps, through CDFW and through CDFW's contractors, shall minimize effects to the SMHM, CRR, CLT, WSP, and longfin smelt DPS to the fullest extent possible.

Term and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure that the applicants comply with the following term and condition, which implement its respective reasonable and prudent measure described above. This term and condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. The Corps, through CDFW and through CDFW's contractors, shall implement the *Conservation Measures* as described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* and comply with this biological opinion.
 - b. The Corps, through CDFW and through CDFW's contractors, shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and *Term and Condition* in this biological opinion.
 - c. The Corps, through CDFW and through CDFW's contractors, shall ensure that all personnel associated with the project comply with the *Reporting Requirements* below.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Corps, through CDFW and through CDFW's contractors, shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinstate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the *Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and CNDDDB (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/BIOS>).

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation for the Eden Landing Ecological Reserve Operations and Maintenance Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
- (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

- (1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
- (2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Brian Hansen, Senior Fish and Wildlife Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 2025-0079689-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

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Personal Communications:

Ben Pearl, Plover and Tern Program Director, SFBBO. Email to Brook Vinnedge, Conservation Scientist, regarding California least tern nesting success in ELER.

Jennifer McBroom, Program Manager at Olofson Environmental, Inc. Email sent to Renee Spenst, Regional Biologist at Ducks Unlimited. September 17, 2021.

Jennifer McBroom, Program Manager at Olofson Environmental, Inc. Email sent to Renee Spenst, Regional Biologist at Ducks Unlimited. October 28, 2021.